

Influence of seedling age on rice yield

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During 1979 sornavari and samba seasons, the performance of short- and medium-duration rice varieties was studied in relation to seedling age in sandy loam soils of PES, Tirurkuppam. The previous finding that 25-day-old seedlings are best had to be confirmed with reference to different soil and agro-climatic regions. Short-duration (ADT31 and TKM9) and medium-duration varieties (IR20 and ASDIS) at four seedling ages were tested. Sprouted seeds

Grain yield of short- and medium-duration varieties at 4 seedling ages during 2 seasons in 1979. PES, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India.

Season and variety	Grain yield (t/ha) of seedlings aged				CD (P = 0.05)
	25 d	30 d	35 d	40 d	
<i>Sornavari</i>					
ADT31	3.87	4.05	4.22	4.42	
TKM9	4.16	4.60	5.26	5.70	0.8
<i>Samba</i>					
IR20	3.02	3.24	3.30	3.37	
ASD15	2.82	2.91	2.98	3.02	N.S.

were treated with diammonium phosphate 3%.

The yield differences between seedling ages were significant for both the short- and medium-duration varieties (see table). In the short-duration group, ADT31 recorded yields similar for all seedling ages. The yield trend favored older seedlings. In TKM9, the 40- and

35-day-old seedlings recorded higher yields than the 30- and 25-day-old seedlings. In the medium-duration group, the yield differences among the seedling ages were not significant. Thus, seedlings of short- and medium-duration rice varieties up to 40 days of age can be planted to advantage in sandy loam soils. ■

Seed rate and spacing for the rice crop

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The influence of seed rate in wet nursery and spacing on rice grain yield was studied during 1979 sornavari and samba seasons at PES, Tirurkuppam. Previous studies have shown that increasing or decreasing the seed rate beyond 3 kg/40 m² resulted in low yields. The study also aimed to keep the yields high at higher seed rates per unit area by nitrogen (N) placement in the crop (TKM9). The treatments consisted of four seed rates, three times of placement, and two spacings (see table). The N placement in the main field was 75 kg N/ha, given 15, 20, and 25 days after planting in a single dose. Phosphorus and potassium were applied as basal doses as recommended by soil tests.

Results showed that the seed rate of 3 kg/40 m² was optimum. The seedlings raised at that rate had optimum physiological growth conducive to higher yields. It was also observed that the grain yield of crops planted at

Influence of seed rate, nitrogen placement, and plant spacing on grain yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1979 sornavari	1979 samba
<i>Seed rates</i>		
1.0 kg/m ² – Pai nursery	5.87	3.60
1.5 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.40	3.61
3.0 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.71	3.91
6.0 kg/40m ² – field nursery	6.02	3.50
CD = (P = 0.05)	0.55	0.24
<i>N placement</i>		
75 kg N/ha 15 DT	6.35	3.61
75 kg N/ha 20 DT	6.18	3.73
75 kg N/ha 25 DT	6.22	3.64
CD = (P = 0.05)	NS	NS
<i>Spacings</i>		
20 x 10	6.44	3.97
20 x 20 cm	6.07	3.34
CD = (P = 0.05)	NS	0.17

^aDT = days after transplanting.

different seed rates was not affected by N applications. The closer spacing of 20 × 10 cm or 50 hills/m² gave higher

yields, which appeared to be optimum for all short-duration varieties like TKM9 (105 days). ■

Growth of azolla with rice and its effect on rice yield

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Azolla is a useful green manure crop. Its nitrogen-fixing activity is due to an endophytic blue-green alga. When azolla is continuously cropped, it can produce molecular nitrogen of as much

as 500 kg/ha annually. In the rice field, azolla growth is fast at the rice crop's early stage, but declines later because of shading by the rice canopy. Widening the distance between rice plant rows will allow the growing of azolla during the whole growth period of wetland rice. This technique was tried experimentally in China.

At IRRI, rice was grown in a 35-m² plot in a wide-narrow row spacing.